

Are quality assessments in science affected by numerical anchors that are not related to quality? Empirical results from a survey of authors assessing previously cited papers

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Many studies have investigated anchoring effects. Anchoring occurs when initial values are used by humans as starting points in assessments. We investigated the prevalence of anchoring effects in the quality assessments of scientific papers. In a survey, we asked corresponding authors to assess the quality of articles they have cited in previous papers. The respondents were randomly assigned to several experimental groups receiving numerical anchors (related or not related to quality). Our results show that there is a small, but statistically significant effect of a random number (numerical access code to the questionnaire) presented to the respondents. Similar to other studies that have investigated the existence of anchoring effects in assessments, our study could demonstrate the existence of an anchoring effect in research evaluation. Researchers seem to be influenced by numbers – i.e., numbers without any relationship to the quality of the evaluated paper – in their assessment of papers.

1. Background and purpose

Many studies have investigated anchoring effects in various contexts. Following Tversky and Kahneman (1974), anchoring occurs when initial values are used by humans as starting points in estimations: numerical starting points distort (numerical) assessments. In order to demonstrate the effect of anchoring, Tversky and Kahneman (1974) asked interviewed persons to estimate the percentage of African nations in the United Nations (UN). In the persons' presence, a wheel of fortune was spun to receive a random number between 0 and 100. In the first instruction, the interviewed persons should indicate whether the random number is higher or lower than the African nations' percentage "by moving upward or downward from the given number" (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974, p. 1128). In the second instruction, they were requested to estimate the percentage. The results of the experiment revealed a significant effect of the random numbers on the estimates: "For example, the median estimates of the percentage of African countries in the United Nations were 25 and 45 for groups that received 10 and 65, respectively, as starting points" (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974, p. 1128).

Overviews of the many studies that have investigated anchoring effects can be found in Mussweiler, Englich, and Strack (2004), Furnham and Boo (2011), Bahník, Englich, and Strack (2017), and Bahník, Mussweiler, and Strack (2021). The literature overviews come to similar conclusions with respect to the prevalence of anchoring effects: These effects belong to the most robust and best replicated findings in psychology. Bornmann, Ganser, and Tekles (2023) were the first to study whether anchoring effects also affect assessments in research. Following the design of a study by Teplitskiy, Duede, Menietti, and Lakhani (2022), they asked corresponding authors to assess the quality of articles they have cited in previous papers. The respondents, who were randomly assigned to one of four experimental groups, received one of three stimuli as anchor information: paper citation impact information, citation impact information on the publishing journal, or a numerical access code to enter the survey. The control group did not receive any of this information. Bornmann et al. (2023) found that quality

assessments depended on the paper impact information, but not on the journal impact information or the access code. The results point to a possible existence of anchoring effects in research assessments.

The design of the study by Bornmann et al. (2023) was limited yet because articles were not assessed by multiple respondents. Only if many respondents assess the same paper, the true, unobservable quality of the papers can be controlled. In the current follow-up study, we addressed this limitation and some other remaining questions from the previous study by using an optimized and extended research design. The purpose of this study is thus to focus stronger on possible causal relations between quality assessments and information presented to the interviewed persons and to investigate more rigorously the existence of possible anchoring effects in research evaluation. The study was pre-registered by the journal *PLOS ONE* (Bornmann & Ganser, 2023); the study contributes to the topic “Practices of evaluation and assessment” of the Science and Technology Indicators (STI) conference 2024. Anchoring effects are able to distort the research evaluation practice, since the evaluation is affected by factors that are not or only partly quality-related.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Research design

Between December 2023 and March 2024, we undertook a survey of corresponding authors with an available email address in the Web of Science database. The corresponding authors received an email with a link to a web-based questionnaire with the request to assess the quality of a paper that they cited some years ago. They were randomly assigned to one of five groups which received (or not)

- (1) information about the (true) citation impact of the paper as an anchor with possibly relevant information for the quality assessment (the author was informed about the use of the citation impact as possible anchor in this study in the invitation email),
- (2) information about the (true) citation impact of the paper (the author was not informed about the use of the citation impact as anchor),
- (3) a randomly generated anchor (an access code to the questionnaire) that is not related to the quality of publications (the author was informed about the use of the access code as anchor) or
- (4) a randomly generated anchor (an access code to the questionnaire; the author was not informed about the use of the access code as anchor).
- (5) A fifth group of authors did not receive any additional information that may function as anchor.

Respondents were first asked whether they remembered the presented paper (previously cited). If not, up to three alternative cited papers were presented to them. Further questions referred to how well they knew the paper which was assessed, and how much it influenced the citing article. In the most important part of the questionnaire, the respondents were first asked whether the quality assessment is higher or lower than the presented access code or citation count, respectively. Second, the respondents rated the paper with respect to several characteristics: overall quality, novelty (departed significantly from what is usually done in this research area), significance (addressed an important topic), validity (designed and performed very well, produced very credible results), generalizability (easily applicable to other contexts), and canonical or prominent reference (the standard reference for this topic; the terms canonical and prominent were randomized, following Teplitskiy et al., 2022). The range of the rating scale was from 1 (bad) to 100 (excellent).

We included in our study cited papers from 2010 that belong to the 1% most frequently cited papers in their publication year and subject category. The main reason for the decision to

include elder papers with many citations was to make sure that we receive multiple ratings for each paper (since many cited papers and citing authors exist). The range of the quality assessment scores is from 1 to 100. The citation counts and access codes that are used in the study are nearly in the same range. Many highly cited papers in our sample have high citation counts, i.e. higher than the range of possible quality assessment scores. Some highly cited papers have no or only one citation in the first three (five) years after publication. To prevent the possibility that the citation counts are out of the range (with respect to the corresponding quality assessment scores), we decided not to consider cited papers in the planned study with citation counts lower than 2 and higher than 99.

2.2. Sample

In total, 12,041 participants answered our questionnaire and provided assessments of the quality of the presented (previously cited) papers. This corresponds to a response rate of 2.84 %, which seems to be low but in the range we expected from Bornmann et al. (2023). 4,704 papers have been assessed by the respondents. On average, each paper received 2.6 ratings but the distribution of ratings is skewed. While the maximum of ratings per paper is 36, 66.2% of the papers received only 1 or 2 ratings. 1,339 papers received between 3 and 6 ratings (see Table 1 for details).

Table 1. Number of ratings per paper.

Number of ratings	Papers (absolute)	Papers (in percent)
1	1,959	41.7
2	1,152	24.5
3	622	13.2
4	361	7.7
5	238	5.1
6	118	2.5
7	87	1.9
8	40	0.9
9	26	0.6
10+	101	2.2
Total	4,704	100.0

Because we have repeated measures for the cited articles in our dataset, we computed multilevel models. We examined treatment effect heterogeneity by estimating fixed effects regression models, including the values of the treatments. This allows us to compare effect sizes of the treatments with the control condition. The model is specified as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{quality assessment}_{ij} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{condition2}_{ij} + \beta_2 \text{condition3}_{ij} + \beta_3 \text{condition4}_{ij} + \beta_4 \text{condition1} \\
 &\cdot \text{value} + \beta_5 \text{condition2} \cdot \text{value} + \beta_6 \text{condition3} \cdot \text{value} + \beta_7 \text{condition4} \cdot \text{value} \\
 &+ u_j + e_{ij}
 \end{aligned}$$

where “condition” 1 to 4 are the four treatment conditions (see above). “value” is the numerical value of the respective information presented to the respondents.

To facilitate the interpretation of the results, this model does not include a main effect for “value”, but four interactions. The coefficients of the interaction terms represent the effects of the “value” on the quality assessments for the four treatments. In the results section, we refer

to these interactions, because the main effects of the conditions are not the foci of our research questions.

3. Results

3.1. Effects of presented values on quality assessments

Figure 1 shows predicted values (with 95% confidence intervals, CIs) of the overall quality assessments depending on the number (e.g., citation counts) presented to the respondents for the four groups in our survey. The average of the quality assessments by the respondents in the control group who assessed the papers without number presentations is additionally included in the figure.

Figure 1. Predicted quality assessments depending on presented numbers (adjusted predictions with 95% confidence intervals).
The control group assessed the papers without number presentations.

The analysis reveals that there is a small, yet statistically highly significant ($p < .001$) positive effect of the access code presented to the respondents on the overall quality assessment. An increase in the access code of ten points (on a scale from 1 to 99) leads to an increase of the assessments by 0.7 points, if the usage of the code as an anchor is revealed to the respondent. The access code leads to an increase of 1 point, if the usage as an anchor is not revealed. Citation counts show no statistically significant effects, regardless of whether their use as an anchor was disclosed or not.

Figure 2. Effects of presented numbers on assessments of various aspects of quality.

For the detailed quality aspects (novelty, significance, validity, generalizability, and canonical reference), the pattern substantially hold what we found for the overall quality. Figure 2 shows that citation counts revealed as an anchor to the respondents does not have statistically significant effects except for “prominent”. When the citation counts’ use as an anchor is not revealed, citation counts have no statistically significant effects. For the access code revealed as an anchor, there is a statistically significant effect on four of the seven outcome variables (overall quality, significance, validity, and generalizability). The effects on the assessments of “significance” and “validity” are statistically significant at the 0.05 level, while the p -value of the effect on the assessment of “generalizability” is 0.008. Access codes which are not revealed as anchors have statistically significant effects on the assessments of all aspects of quality except for “prominent”. For “generalizability”, the p -value is 0.001, for the other aspects the effects are statistically highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Since “canonical” and “prominent” were presented only to one half of the respondents each, the p values should not be compared with the other quality aspects. The found effect sizes are small in all models that we estimated. Most of the effects are below 0.1, meaning that an increase in the independent variable of 10 points leads to an increase of the quality assessments of less than one point.

4.2. Robustness

In this section, we briefly describe the results of some robustness checks that we have performed in addition to the results. The checks refer to the model with the overall quality as dependent variable.

Reviews and technical reports

While we selected only papers of the type “article” for our sample, some respondents alerted us that we asked them to rate review articles or technical reports. Since the Web of Science

database use other document type categorizations than publishers, such feedback from respondents is understandable. Reviews and technical reports are usually cited very often but for other reasons than original research articles (e.g., reviews give an overview of the research in a field or on a topic). The different motives to cite reviews and technical reports might bias our results. Our results show, however, that the exclusion of 210 articles with one or more of the terms “review”, “overview”, “meta-analysis”, “technical”, and “report” in the title of the papers does not alter the results substantially.

Citation numbers

In the survey, we presented “valid” citation counts to the respondents from the first 3 or 5 years after the appearance of the cited publication. Respondents might have doubted the presented citations counts (e.g., they may have the impression that the number is too low). In the end of the questionnaire, therefore, we asked the respondents whether they searched for the number of citations themselves. Excluding the 979 respondents who did not answer this question with “no” (these respondents could have searched for the citation counts) does not alter the results substantially. Furthermore, we excluded in another analysis the ratings for the 72 cited papers, where the citation counts up to 2021 are more than 20 times higher than the citation counts presented in the survey (the presented low numbers may have irritated the respondents). This exclusion also had no substantial effect on the regression results.

5. Discussion

In our study, we investigated the prevalence of anchoring effects in the quality assessments of papers. Our results show that there is a small, but statistically significant effect of a random number (access code) presented to the respondents. This effect was stronger when the respondents did not know that the random number is used as an anchor. When this anchor was revealed, there were fewer statistically significant effects on the assessments of various quality aspects and the effect sizes were even smaller. There were scarcely effects of citation counts presented to the respondents as possible anchors, regardless of whether the respondents were informed about their use as an anchor or not. The missing effects of citation counts (compared to the effects of the random number) seem surprising because citations are seen as at least weakly correlated with the quality of papers (see, e.g., Diekmann, Näf, & Schubiger, 2012). In the interpretation of the results, it should be considered yet that the quality of the papers was controlled in the analyses by using fixed effects models: In the statistical analyses, only the interactions of the within variation of the numerical value – that were presented to the respondents with the respective condition – were considered. The results seem thus to confirm the relationship of citation counts and quality. Otherwise we would have observed in the results an “additional” effect of the citation counts.

Similar to other studies that have investigated the existence of anchoring effects in human assessments, our study – with an optimized design of the previous study by Bornmann et al. (2023) – could demonstrate the existence of an anchoring effect in research evaluation. Researchers seem to be influenced by numbers – i.e., numbers without any relationship to the quality of the evaluated paper – in their assessment of papers. In contrast to many other studies, this study revealed yet only a small effect of the access code used by the participants in the survey. An increase in the access code of ten points leads to an increase of the assessments by one point, if the usage of the code as an anchor is not revealed to the respondent. Since the papers in this study have been assessed on a rating scale from 1 to 99, we estimate the practical relevance of our results as low: there seems to be a low risk (in peer review) that assessments of papers are substantially influenced by (randomly) available numbers that are not related to the process of assessment.

Open science practices

Our study was preregistered (Bornmann & Ganser, 2023) in *PLOS ONE*, a multi-disciplinary open access journal. A full paper with detailed findings of our study will be submitted to *PLOS ONE*. The data underlying our analysis will be made available in a repository (when the full paper will be accepted by *PLOS ONE*).

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: Lutz Bornmann, Christian Ganser.

Formal analysis: Christian Ganser.

Investigation: Lutz Bornmann, Christian Ganser.

Methodology: Lutz Bornmann, Christian Ganser.

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Competing interests

We have no competing interests to declare.

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